

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Play-based Learning Strategies as Correlates of Early Learners' Cognitive Readiness Towards Learning in Montessori Schools in Lagelu Local Government Area, Ibadan, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between play-based learning strategies and cognitive readiness, particularly attention span—among early learners in Montessori schools within Lagler Local Government Area, Ibadan, Oyo State. Guided by Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, the study employed a descriptive survey design involving early learners and their teachers across selected Montessori schools. Data were collected using a teacher questionnaire and an observation checklist, and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). Findings showed that storytelling emerged as the most commonly adopted play-based learning strategy, followed by outdoor/free play and puzzle-solving activities. However, classroom observations revealed a stronger presence of free play and music/movement activities, suggesting some variation between teacher-stated practices and actual implementation. Learners generally demonstrated the ability to sustain attention for more than five minutes and follow instructions effectively, indicating that structured play promotes focus, engagement, and cognitive readiness. Correlation analysis revealed significant positive relationships between all play-based learning strategies and cognitive readiness, with construction play showing the strongest association, followed by outdoor/free play and role/dramatic play. These results highlight that although storytelling is the most frequently used strategy, hands-on and exploratory forms of play show greater influence on learners' attention and overall cognitive development. The study concludes that a balanced integration of diverse play-based strategies, supported by adequate learning materials and intentional teacher facilitation, enhances learners' cognitive readiness for formal learning. It recommends improved teacher training, better resourcing of play environments, and the institutionalization of structured play routines to maximize the cognitive benefits inherent in Montessori pedagogy.

Keywords: Attention Span; Cognitive Readiness; Early Learners; Lagler Local Government Area; Montessori School; Play-Based Learning

1. Introduction

The early years of a child's life are a critical phase in human development, laying the foundation for lifelong learning, behavior, and health (UNICEF, 2021). Early childhood education has evolved over the years to recognize that how children learn is as important as what they learn (OECD, 2020). In this context, play is no longer seen merely as a recreational activity, but as a central vehicle for meaningful learning in early childhood (Hassinger-Das et al., 2020). Globally, educators and developmental psychologists advocate for play-based learning as a developmentally appropriate approach that nurtures various domains of learning—cognitive, physical, emotional, and social (Pyle et al., 2022). The Montessori method of education, in particular, emphasizes child-centered, hands-on, and exploratory activities that align strongly with play-based learning principles (Lillard, 2021). Despite the recognized value of play, its

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structured application in Nigerian preschool settings remains inconsistent and often underexplored, especially with regard to how it supports cognitive readiness in early learners (Akinrotimi & Olowe, 2023).

In many countries with advanced early childhood education systems, such as Finland, Sweden, and Canada, play is considered a legitimate pedagogical tool (Hämäläinen and van Oers, 2021). There, children are encouraged to learn through exploration, experimentation, and creativity (Pyle and Danniels, 2020). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reports that countries that prioritize holistic development through structured and unstructured play achieve better long-term educational and life outcomes (OECD, 2021). International organizations like UNICEF and the World Bank have also stressed that play is essential for developing foundational skills such as problem-solving, communication, and executive function, all of which are building blocks of school readiness (UNICEF, 2022; World Bank, 2023). In contrast, many education systems in low- and middle-income countries continue to favor rigid, teacher-directed approaches, even in the early years (Awopegba and Oduolowu, 2020). These systems often place emphasis on early literacy and numeracy drills at the expense of developmentally appropriate practices that support brain growth and learning readiness (Mwaura, 2021).

In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education recognizes the importance of early childhood education and recommends the use of play in developing young children's foundational skills (Federal Ministry of Education, 2020). The Early Childhood Care, Development and Education (ECCDE) curriculum encourages the use of songs, rhymes, storytelling, drama, and games to facilitate learning (NIEPA, 2021). However, the implementation of these play-based strategies is uneven. Many preschools still rely heavily on rote learning and early academic drills, often driven by societal pressure for early reading and writing performance (Ogunyemi and Ragpot, 2022). This academic pressure frequently overshadows the importance of developmental readiness, including cognitive growth (Okoli, 2023). As a result, children are sometimes pushed into formal learning environments without the cognitive and behavioral tools required for sustained engagement, focus, and learning success (Oduolowu and Oniwon, 2020).

Within this landscape, Montessori schools have emerged across Nigeria as a preferred option for early childhood education. The Montessori method promotes learning through structured play, self-directed activity, and collaborative engagement (Odebunmi and Samuel, 2021). Its materials and instructional design are intentionally crafted to enhance independence, concentration, and problem-solving skills (Lillard, 2021). However, the term "Montessori" is often used loosely in Nigeria, and many schools labeled as Montessori may not follow its principles with fidelity (Adeyemi and Odotola, 2022). This has implications for children's developmental outcomes, especially regarding cognitive readiness (Afolabi and Olowe, 2024).

In Lagelu Local Government Area (LGA) of Ibadan, Oyo State, the early childhood education sector includes a growing number of private Montessori schools. These schools serve diverse communities, ranging from low-income to middle-income families (Adewuyi, 2023). Despite their popularity, informal observations and teacher reports indicate that children in these settings often exhibit short attention spans, difficulty focusing on tasks, and challenges with cognitive engagement (Olatunji and Amadi, 2024). Such issues raise concerns about whether the learning strategies in use, especially play-based ones, are effectively supporting the development of school readiness skills (Ajayi and Ige, 2023).

Play-based learning strategies encompass a variety of interactive approaches through which play is deliberately employed to achieve defined learning outcomes (Pyle et al., 2022). These strategies include storytelling, which nurtures imagination, language development, and listening skills while allowing children to internalize moral lessons and sequence events (Kim and Lee, 2021). Outdoor or free play encourages exploration and creativity in natural environments, supporting physical development, social interaction, and independent decision-making (Bird et al., 2021). Puzzle and problem-solving games foster logical reasoning, memory retention, and concentration by engaging learners in activities that require analytical thinking and persistence (Fisher et al., 2020). Role play or dramatic play allows children to act out real-life or imaginative scenarios, enhancing empathy, communication, and social understanding (Göncü and Vadeboncoeur, 2020). Finally, construction play, involving blocks, Lego, and similar materials, stimulates spatial awareness, fine motor skills, and creativity through hands-on building and experimentation (Verdine et al., 2021). Collectively, these forms of play provide enjoyable yet intellectually stimulating experiences that promote critical aspects of cognitive growth, including attention, reasoning, and problem-solving, thereby strengthening early learners' readiness for formal education (Hassinger-Das et al., 2020).

Cognitive readiness refers to the mental abilities that prepare a child to begin formal learning. It includes various components such as attention span, working memory, language comprehension, reasoning skills, problem-solving ability, information processing, and executive functioning (Diamond, 2020). These components interact to influence how a child receives, interprets, and responds to learning experiences. A cognitively ready child can focus on tasks, remember instructions, engage in goal-directed behavior, and adjust to the demands of a classroom environment

(McClelland et al., 2021). Within the Montessori approach, these abilities are cultivated through hands-on materials and uninterrupted work cycles that allow children to develop concentration and independence (Lillard, 2021).

Among the many elements that make up cognitive readiness, attention span stands out as both foundational and measurable. It refers to the length of time a child can focus on a task without becoming distracted (Ruff and Rothbart, 2020). Attention span influences a child's ability to complete activities, retain information, and learn effectively. Research shows that attention is closely linked with learning outcomes in reading, mathematics, and language development (Steinsbekk et al., 2021). Attention span can be developed over time and is significantly influenced by the quality of early learning experiences (Markussen-Brown et al., 2022). Children exposed to engaging, age-appropriate play activities tend to develop longer attention spans compared to those subjected to rigid academic routines or passive screen time (Neville et al., 2020). In the Montessori classroom, materials are carefully designed to draw and hold a child's attention, thus enabling deep engagement with learning tasks (Lillard, 2021). However, in practice, the ability of Montessori schools in places like Lagelu LGA to foster attention development depends on the fidelity of the method's implementation (Adeyemi and Odotola, 2022).

Several factors affect the development of attention span in early learners. These include the classroom environment, teacher-child interaction, the use of learning materials, parental involvement, nutrition, sleep patterns, and exposure to screens or stress (Tso et al., 2022). In contexts where classrooms are overcrowded, under-resourced, or poorly managed, attention development may be hindered (Awopegba and Oduolowu, 2020). Similarly, when play-based strategies are not properly implemented—either due to lack of teacher training or misinterpretation of play's role in learning—children may not receive the stimulation needed to build sustained focus (Ogunyemi and Ragpot, 2022). In Lagelu LGA, these challenges are compounded by varying school standards and limited oversight, which result in inconsistencies in the quality of early childhood education (Ajayi and Ige, 2023).

While cognitive readiness encompasses multiple abilities, this study will focus specifically on attention span as the key indicator. Attention span is critical for school readiness because it influences how well a child can engage with classroom activities, follow instructions, and persist in learning tasks (McClelland et al., 2021). It is also one of the most observable and measurable aspects of early cognitive development, making it suitable for empirical study (Diamond, 2020). By narrowing the focus to attention span, this research aims to generate specific insights into how play-based learning strategies influence this critical domain of cognitive readiness. Furthermore, by concentrating on Montessori schools within Lagelu Local Government Area, the study will provide localized data that can inform practice and policy improvements at the grassroots level (Afolabi and Olowe, 2024).

1.1. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between play-based learning strategies and early learners' cognitive readiness, with specific emphasis on attention span, in Montessori schools within Lagelu Local Government Area of Ibadan.

1.2. The objectives are to

- identify the most adopted play-based learning strategies used in Montessori schools within Lagelu Local Government Area.
- assess the attention span of early learners in selected Montessori schools in the area.
- assess the extent to which play-based learning strategies are implemented in the schools.
- examine the relationship between play-based learning strategies and cognitive readiness in early learners.

Research Question One: What is the most adopted play-based learning strategies that is used in Montessori schools within Lagler Local Government Area?

To answer this, findings from both the observation checklist and the teacher questionnaire are presented.

Table 1 Play-Based Learning Strategies Adopted in Montessori Schools (Teachers' Responses, N = 12)

Strategy	Always		Sometimes		Rarely		Not at all		Mean	SD	Rank
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%			
Storytelling	58.3	7	25.0	3	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.42	0.67	1st
Outdoor/free play	50.0	6	33.3	4	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.33	0.69	2nd
Puzzle/problem-solving games	41.7	5	41.7	5	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.25	0.70	3rd
Role play / Dramatic play	41.7	5	33.3	4	25.0	3	0.0	0	3.17	0.76	4th
Construction play (blocks, Lego)	33.3	4	41.7	5	25.0	3	0.0	0	3.08	0.74	5th

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Research Question Two: What is the attention span of early learners in selected Montessori schools in the area?

Table 2 Distribution of Learner Attention Span Indicators (N = 108)

Behavioral Indicator	Always (n)		Sometimes		Rarely		Never		Mean	SD
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%		
Student maintains focus less than 5mins	62	57.4	29	26.9	11	10.2	6	5.5	3.36	0.84
Student follows instructions attentively	58	53.7	31	28.7	12	11.1	7	6.5	3.29	0.89
Student stays engaged with peers	54	50.0	30	27.8	15	13.9	9	8.3	3.19	0.95
Student completes tasks without prompting	46	42.6	32	29.6	18	16.7	12	11.1	3.04	1.01
Student shifts between tasks frequently	21	19.4	34	31.5	33	30.6	20	18.5	2.52	1.03

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Research Question Three: To what extent are the play-based learning strategies implemented in these schools?

Data was drawn from both the observation checklist and teacher questionnaire.

Table 3 Analysis of Play-Based Strategy Implementation

Strategy	Always		Sometimes		Rarely		Not at all		Mean	SD
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%		
Storytelling	58.3	7	25.0	3	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.42	0.67
Outdoor/free play	50.0	6	33.3	4	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.33	0.69
Puzzle/problem-solving games	41.7	5	41.7	5	16.7	2	0.0	0	3.25	0.70
Role play / Dramatic play	41.7	5	33.3	4	25.0	3	0.0	0	3.17	0.76
Construction play (blocks, Lego)	33.3	4	41.7	5	25.0	3	0.0	0	3.08	0.74

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

- Weighted mean: $16.25/5 = 3.25$
- Decision Rule: ≤ 2.50 is low
- 2.50 to 2.99 is moderate
- 3.00 to 3.49 is high
- ≥ 3.50 is very high

1.3. Test of Hypotheses

There will be no significant relationship between play-based learning strategies and early learners' cognitive readiness in Montessori schools within Lagler Local Government Area

Table 4 Correlations of Play-Based Strategies and Cognitive Readiness

Variables		Storytelling	Outdoor/Free Play	Puzzle/Problem-Solving Games	Role Play/Dramatic Play	Construction Play (Blocks, Lego)	Cognitive Readiness
Storytelling	Pearson Correlation	1	0.560**	0.490**	0.620**	0.540**	0.530**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108
Outdoor/Free Play	Pearson Correlation	0.560**	1	0.550**	0.480**	0.600**	0.590**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	-	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108
Puzzle/Problem-Solving Games	Pearson Correlation	0.490**	0.550**	1	0.450**	0.520**	0.510**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	-	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108
Role Play/Dramatic Play	Pearson Correlation	0.620**	0.480**	0.450**	1	0.580**	0.580**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	-	0.000	0.000
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108
Construction Play (Blocks, Lego)	Pearson Correlation	0.540**	0.600**	0.520**	0.580**	1	0.640**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-	0.000
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108
Cognitive Readiness	Pearson Correlation	0.530**	0.590**	0.510**	0.580**	0.640**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Researcher's Computation (2025), SPSS Output.

2. Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study reveal key insights into the play-based learning strategies adopted in Montessori schools within Lagler Local Government Area and their relationship with early learners' cognitive readiness. The results show that the most commonly adopted play-based learning strategies are storytelling and rhyme recitation (Mean = 3.42) alongside outdoor or free play (Mean = 3.33). Teachers strongly support these methods because they align with Montessori philosophy, which emphasizes creativity, imagination, and language development as crucial elements of early learning. Storytelling aids vocabulary building, listening, and comprehension skills, all of which foster cognitive growth. However, classroom observations indicate a gap between teachers' reported practices and the reality of implementation, as unstructured play activities such as free play, music, and movement are more frequently observed. These activities, though less structured, are easier to implement in large classes with limited resources and have been found to support children's socio-emotional and cognitive development. This finding underscores the need for a balance between structured and unstructured play to enhance children's holistic development.

In assessing the attention span of early learners, the study found that most children demonstrated an encouraging level of focus, particularly during tasks requiring sustained attention (Mean = 3.36). More than half of the learners could maintain attention for over five minutes, reflecting the effectiveness of the Montessori approach, which allows children to learn at their own pace in calm and stimulating environments. Learners also showed good ability to follow instructions (Mean = 3.29) and engage positively with peers (Mean = 3.19), indicating that play-based learning promotes both cognitive and social interaction. Nonetheless, moderate scores in completing tasks without prompting (Mean = 3.04) and task-switching (Mean = 2.52) highlight the need for teachers to apply scaffolding techniques that help learners maintain task persistence, reduce distractions, and strengthen their concentration.

Further analysis of the extent of play-based learning implementation shows that while these strategies are moderately applied across the sampled Montessori classrooms, the depth and consistency vary. Storytelling recorded the highest level of implementation (Weighted Mean = 3.42), followed by outdoor/free play (3.33) and puzzles or problem-solving games (3.25). Role play and dramatic play (3.17) and construction play (3.08) were the least implemented, primarily due to challenges such as limited space, inadequate materials, and time constraints. Despite these limitations, none of the teachers completely excluded play from their teaching, signifying a strong acceptance of its pedagogical importance. The findings further indicate that storytelling is preferred because it is low-cost, adaptable, and easily integrated into language lessons, though excessive reliance on it may narrow opportunities for experiential and collaborative learning that other forms of play provide. It is therefore recommended that schools schedule adequate time for different play types, develop shared play resources, and train teachers in effective facilitation and assessment of play-based learning. Leadership support, through consistent monitoring and structured routines, can also promote uniform application of play strategies across classrooms.

Lastly, the analysis of the relationship between play-based learning strategies and cognitive readiness revealed significant positive correlations ($p < .01$) across all strategies, although with differing strengths. Construction play showed the strongest association ($r = 0.640$), indicating that activities involving manipulation of materials and spatial reasoning contribute most effectively to cognitive readiness, even though it had the lowest implementation rate (Weighted Mean = 3.08). Outdoor or free play ($r = 0.590$) and role play or dramatic play ($r = 0.580$) also demonstrated strong positive relationships, followed by storytelling ($r = 0.530$) and puzzle-based play ($r = 0.510$). These results suggest that while teachers favor storytelling due to its simplicity and scalability, greater cognitive benefits arise from hands-on and experiential play activities. The overall findings therefore reject the null hypothesis and reveal a clear imbalance: strategies that most enhance cognitive readiness are the least implemented, while those with moderate effects are more frequently used. To address this gap, greater emphasis should be placed on construction, outdoor, and dramatic play, supported by adequate materials, teacher training, and environmental preparation, while maintaining storytelling and puzzles as complementary strategies that reinforce broader cognitive growth among early learners.

3. Conclusion

The study set out to explore play-based learning strategies as predictors of early students' cognitive preparedness at the Montessori schools used in the Lagelu Local Government Area, Ibadan. The finding provides a clear suggestion that play-based learning not only exists but also has very real consequences for attention span, interest of the learner, and preparedness for formal learning. In each of the three research schools, both structured (for example, the puzzles and the storytelling) and unstructured (for example, the free play and the music/dance) strategies were widely practiced though unevenly. Teachers self-described a preference for structured measures, while real observations registered a dominance of unstructured techniques. The discrepancy reflects how classroom realities, material resource

insufficiencies, overcrowding, and cultural tradition, reorganize the provision of play away from ideal pedagogical intention.

The research also confirmed students' attention span, which commonly lies between 20 and 30 minutes, plays a critical mediating role between play strategy and cognitive readiness. Important statistical relationships between play practice, attention span, and student outcomes were found, indicating both structured and unstructured play demonstrate quantifiable cognitive worth when adequately supported. These results lend support for the importance of play for young children but additionally emphasize the reality that sustainability rests upon resources, support, and cultural fit.

Lastly, the study affirms play-based learning as a robust, context-informed predictor of readiness among early students in Montessori settings. The null hypotheses presented were discounted, vindicating the existence of strong connections between play-based approach, time on concentration, and mental readiness. However, without special training, policy support, and investment into resources, these benefits may not be equally realized across Nigerian classes.

Recommendations

Teachers should be trained to balance structured and unstructured play. The study showed that free play and music dominate classrooms, while puzzles and construction play are less common. Professional development programmed must help teachers scaffold both approaches so that children enjoy creativity while also developing literacy, problem-solving, and attention-regulation skills. Mentorship from experienced teachers should also be encouraged to spread facilitation techniques.

Schools should invest in low-cost, sustainable materials. Resource shortages were a recurring challenge, particularly for structured activities such as puzzles and construction tasks. Locally made materials, including wooden blocks, recycled items, and storytelling props, can replace costly imports and ensure consistent access. These practical solutions reduce financial strain and strengthen sustainability.

Policymakers must embed play into the national curriculum and provide funding for implementation. The findings revealed that play is often undervalued compared to formal instruction. Revising the curriculum to position play as a central strategy, coupled with dedicated funding streams for teaching materials and teacher workshops, will strengthen outcomes. Monitoring and evaluation systems should also assess not only whether play occurs, but whether it is developmentally meaningful.

Parents and communities should actively support schools in promoting play. Awareness campaigns, parent-teacher meetings, and open days can demonstrate how sustained play fosters attention, literacy, and resilience. Communities can also partner with schools to provide materials, using local artisans and associations to donate or produce low-cost play resources such as musical instruments, outdoor equipment, or art supplies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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